

Sheath rot (ShR) severity due to rice bug infection

P. Lakshmanan, Plant Pathology Department; S. M. Kumar and R. Velusamy, Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute (ACRI), Killikulam, Vallanad 627252 Tamil Nadu, India

A high infestation of rice bugs *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thunb.) (15-20/panicle) was observed at ACRI Sep-Oct 1990. ShR [causal organism:

Sarocladium oryzae (Sawada) W. Gams & D. Hawksw.] incidence was also high.

We conducted a greenhouse study to examine the role of rice bugs in ShR infection. IR20 seeds were sown in 20- × 40-cm peat trays. Four weeks after germination, 2 seedlings/pot were transplanted to 10-cm earthen pots filled with wetland soil. The plants were kept in insect-proof cages in the greenhouse.

Laboratory-reared rice bug masses were collected and released on the plants at booting at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 bugs/tiller, with a no-bug control. After 48 h of feeding, the plants were sprayed to runoff with a spore suspen-

sion of 5×10^7 conidia/ml, and placed immediately in a 100% relative humidity chamber maintained at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. Inoculated plants were then transferred to greenhouse benches.

Each treatment had about 20 tillers with five replications. Individual tillers were evaluated daily for ShR infection using a 0-9 scale (0 = no disease, 1 = less than 1% sheath area affected, 3 = 1-5%;

5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, and 9 = more than 50% sheath area affected).

Bug-infested plants exhibited typical ShR symptoms within 12 d after spraying with spore suspension. Disease incidence was low on noninfested plants. ShR severity and percent of infected tillers were related to bug population (Fig. 1, 2). □

Farm machinery

A simple closed chemical transfer attachment for knapsack sprayers

N. K. Awadhwal, G. R. Quick, and E. F. Cabrido, IIRI

Operators of small sprayers are exposed to pesticides at all stages of use, but especially while measuring and mixing concentrated formulations. The risk of contamination can be minimized by using an alternative system to transfer chemicals from the original container to the sprayer tank.

We developed and tested a simple closed system for transfer of liquid chemicals to knapsack sprayers. It consists of a 1-liter plastic container

fitted with a manually operated piston pump. The pump barrel is transparent and graduated, allowing up to 35 ml pesticide/stroke to be withdrawn from the bottle (see figure). The outlet of the pump is connected to the tank through a nondrip connector that permits flow only when connection is made. The system is mounted to the sprayer tank with a clamp.

We compared operator exposure with this system with two conventional handling methods: mixing a measured quantity of chemical with water in a bucket and then pouring the solution into the tank, and pouring the chemical directly into the sprayer tank. The experiments were laid out in randomized complete block design with five replica-

1. Effect of rice bug population on ShR severity.

Effect of rice bug population on percentage of selected tillers.

Closed chemical transfer system for knapsack sprayer and system attached to a knapsack sprayer.

Operators' exposure and spillage with different transfer methods for pesticides.

Method	Amount ^a (μl)				Total
	Chemical on hand	Spillage on floor	Spillage on tank	Remainder ^b	
Mixing and pouring	42.65 b	425.15 a	18.73 a	69.60 a	556.13 a
Pouring in tank	72.55 a	129.70 b	5.45 b	47.40 c	255.10 b
Closed system	15.95 c	25.80 c	1.73 c	65.82 b	109.30 c

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT ($P < 0.05$). ^b Chemical that remained adhering to the closed transfer system, measuring cylinder, or the bucket after one rinsing at the end of each test.

lions. An aqueous solution of fluorescent dye was used instead of pesticide. The sprayer operator wore clean gloves to collect contamination on hands. All horizontal surfaces in the work area were covered with polythene sheeting to collect spillage. We used absorbent paper to wipe clean spillage on the sprayer. The dye was washed from each item with

water. We used a Fluorometer (Sequoi-Turner model 450) to determine dye content.

Results show that the averages for hand contamination, spillage on the work area floor, and volume of chemical wiped from the sprayer tank and exposed surface of the connector were significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) for the closed

chemical transfer system than for the other methods (see table). The mean volume of chemical that remained on the system at the end of a test was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than the remainder in the measuring cylinders and bucket in the other methods. Total spills and exposure were significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) for the closed system—a fivefold reduction.

The closed chemical transfer system reduces the frequency of handling concentrated chemicals from the usual 8-12 times/d to only 1-2 times/d. This system also minimizes the quantity of unused diluted chemical and thus reduces the problem of disposing of surpluses. The system can be fabricated in small workshops and marketed for about US\$10, or could be readily incorporated into a new sprayer design. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Irrigation and drainage congress

The 15th Congress of the International Commission on Irrigation and Drainage (ICID) will be in The Hague, The

Netherlands, 30 Aug- 11 Sep 1993. Water management in the next century is the theme. The 7th International Exhibition on Irrigation, Drainage, and Flood Control takes place during the congress.

For information contact Netherlands National Committee ICID, Bart Schultz, P.O. Box 600,8200 AP LELYSTAD, The Netherlands, Telephone: 31 3200 97440, Fax: 31 3200 34300, Telex: 40115 flevo nl. □

Effective irrigation management course

Effective Irrigation Management will be held at the University of Southampton, 28 Sep-16 Oct 1992. The intensive course is for professionals involved in management and performance assessment of irrigation and related water resources schemes in developing countries. The Institute of Irrigation Studies at the University of Southampton and HR, Wallingford sponsor the course.

For information, contact the Course Administrator, Effective Irrigation Management Short Course, Institute of Irrigation Studies, The University, Southampton SO9 5NH, United Kingdom. Tel: 0703-593728. Telex: 47661 (a/b sotonu g). Fax: 0703-593017

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New publications

Field-crop ecosystems. C.J. Pearson, ed. Vol. 18 of *Ecosystems of the world*. Examines how agriculturalists and ecologists look at field-crop ecosystems and attempt better management of these systems with the aid of computer modeling.

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